

Agar-based aqueous electrolytes for electrochemical capacitors with reduced self-discharge

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports on the electrochemical performance of symmetric carbon/carbon electrochemical capacitors operating in aqueous electrolyte (0.5 mol L⁻¹ K₂SO₄ solution) and modified with various amounts of agar (up to 5 wt%). It has been found that a change in electrolyte form (from liquid to gel-like) increases the hydrogen storage efficiency on the negative electrode (confirmed by *operando* Raman spectroscopy), improves the cycle life at elevated voltages and reduces the self-discharge. Furthermore, it has been found that the gas generation rate during capacitor operation is remarkably diminished (by ca. 4 times), and thus, the detrimental impact of increased internal pressure is noticeably reduced.

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1. Introduction

Dramatic increases in current world energy consumption, together with increasing awareness of environmental protection, have induced interest in the development of renewable energy sources, such as sunlight, wind or tides [1–7]. However, being able to cover most of the energy demand with renewable resources (for short time periods) does not solve the problem of unpredictable weather fluctuations [6–8]. This issue requires conventional power plants to be always ready for operation and does not diminish the carbon footprint. Despite the significant progress and large investment in novel and clean energy production technologies, the lack of cheap, sustainable and large-scale energy storage systems is still an urgent issue [7,9]. Among the variety of energy storage systems, electrochemical capacitors are in favour due to their excellent life span (millions of cycles), environmentally friendly character (in the case of aqueous electrolytes and bio-sourced binders) and fast charge-discharge rate [10–12]. Typically, electrochemical capacitors are constructed of two highly porous electrodes soaked in a liquid electrolyte and separated by a dielectric membrane. However, the major drawback of electrochemical capacitors is their relatively fast self-discharge, attributed to the

charge redistribution in differently shaped pores induced by high ion mobility in liquid electrolytes [13–15]. Thus, a solution to this problem might be the replacement of liquid electrolytes by solid-polymer electrolytes.

Over the years, the application of solid-polymer and gel electrolytes in energy storage devices has been extensively studied [16–26], including the exploitation of proton-exchange membranes such as Nafion® [27–32]. In the battery field, the most common approach involves the direct dissolution of lithium salts in the ion-coordination polymer [33–35]. For electrochemical capacitors, the most commonly used polymers are poly(vinyl alcohol), PVA [25,36–38], and poly(ethylene oxide), PEO [39,40]. However, capacitors operating with such electrolytes have been criticized for low electrochemical performance, most likely originating from increased resistance and low ionic conductivity in comparison to those obtained with liquid counterparts.

Moreover, the application of these polymers requires corrosive electrolytes, such as H₂SO₄, LiCl or H₃PO₄.

Currently, a group of bio-sourced polymers as modifiers of electrolytic media for electrochemical capacitors has attracted scientific interest. Over the years, a great variety of environmentally friendly materials, such as gelatine, sodium alginate, chitin, chitosan and hydrocellulose, have been tested as gelling agents [41], with sodium alginate being the most widely applied. This compound was introduced in 2010 by Ishikawa et al., who demonstrated an electrochemical capacitor operating with alginate-ionic

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liquid gel electrolytes [42,43]. The electrolyte was prepared by wet-casting 1, 2 or 3 wt% alginate aqueous solution with a cross-linking agent. The gel-like film was then washed and immersed in [EMIm][BF₄] or [TEMA][BF₄] ionic liquid. After residual water removal, the gel was used as an electrolyte/membrane. It has been demonstrated that high alginate affinity towards carbon electrode materials results in better electrochemical performance, and this improvement is achieved because of the use of solid electrolyte instead of liquid electrolyte. Further research on alginate-based electrolytes has focused on the preparation of aqueous solutions as gel precursors and their in situ gelation on the electrode material surface [44–46]. Several related approaches have been proposed to prepare so-called bio-hydrogels. Aleman et al. prepared a solid-state capacitor by in situ gelation of alginate-based electrolyte on PEDOT electrodes. However, the system was characterized by a limited voltage (0.8 V) and significant self-discharge. Another approach was presented by Guo et al.; in their work, sodium alginate was dissolved in water, and the resulting hydrogel was utilized as an electrolyte. The system demonstrated very good electrochemical performance, but the capacitor voltage was limited to 1.0 V.

Another bio-polymer proposed to date is chitosan. Similar to alginate-based electrolytes, chitosan has been applied in aqueous and ionic liquid-based media. Ishikawa et al. presented a chitosan-based membrane immersed in [EMIm][BF₄] [26]. The preparation procedure was similar to that described for alginate, but in this case, the authors used a 2 wt% solution of chitosan in the initial step. The electrochemical capacitors with chitosan-[EMIm][BF₄] gel electrolyte displayed remarkably improved capacitance, attributed to the high ionic conductivity and good affinity of the membrane to the carbon material. Subramanian et al. presented a procedure in which a membrane/electrolyte was prepared by casting 2% (wt./vol.) water-based solution, followed by drying under ambient conditions. Then, the solid layer was immersed in the aqueous electrolyte solution to promote ion adsorption. Afterwards, the solid electrolytes were used to assemble electrochemical capacitors. The maximum reported voltage of the system was 1.0 V, and the long-term stability was moderate; during long-term charging/discharging, a drop in electrode active surface area and membrane degradation were observed [47].

Recently, to improve the electrochemical performance of polymer-based capacitors, the application of agar-based hydrogels has been reported [48,49]. Agar is a naturally abundant, biocompatible gelling agent derived from seaweeds. The main components in the agar structure are agarose (Scheme 1) and agarpectin (Scheme 2).

In aqueous solution, agar dissolves at temperatures above 90 °C and solidifies after cooling below 45 °C. Hydrogels obtained from agar are characterized by a porous structure (pore size 400–500 nm) and high elasticity [50]. During the gelation of agar, cross linking and self-assembly of ions occur through hydrogen bonds. Due to the high water content and combined porous structure, agar hydrogels are capable of providing high ion mobility and thus high conductivity [51]. In previously reported systems, NaCl salt has been selected as a charge carrier within the agar

Scheme 1. Chair representation of agarose monomer composed of D-galactose and 3,6-anhydro-L-galactopyranose.

Scheme 2. Chair representation of agarpectin monomer composed of D-glucuronic acid and pyruvic acid.

matrix. However, the systems again demonstrated high internal resistance and limited operating voltage. Thus, the improvement of electrolyte properties appears to be crucial for the further development of environmentally friendly gel-like electrolytes for electrochemical capacitors.

In this work, a symmetric carbon/carbon capacitor with a K₂SO₄-based agar gel electrolyte is proposed. It is believed that joining the positive properties of SO₄²⁻-based electrolytes with the promising properties of agar will result in an overall improvement in capacitor performance, in terms of both specific energy and self-discharge rate. Taking into consideration the following formula for the energy (E) of electrochemical capacitors:

$$E = 0.5 C U_{\max}^2$$

an increase in the capacitance (C) and maximum voltage (U_{max}) results in a remarkable increase in the energy stored by the device.

As previously reported, sulfate-based electrolytes allow electrochemical capacitors to operate above the water decomposition voltage at 1.23 V; for systems equipped with gold current collectors, which decrease the negative aspects of corrosion, a voltage of 2.2 V has been reached [52–55]. In addition to enhanced voltage, one can expect improved capacitance (pseudocapacitance) on the negative electrode, originating from hydrogen storage phenomena.

In this paper, we report on the electrochemical performance of symmetric carbon/carbon supercapacitors with gel-like, agar-based electrolytes. The systems demonstrate stable performance at a voltage of 1.6 V at room temperature. By three-electrode cell and *operando* Raman spectroscopy investigations, the positive impact of gel-like electrolytes on the hydrogen sorption/desorption process was confirmed. Moreover, the internal pressure build-up and self-discharge of the capacitor were remarkably diminished.

2. Experimental

2.1. Electrode and electrolyte preparation

Self-standing, circular electrodes (Ø = 10 mm, 9.5 mg) were cut from activated carbon fabric (Kynol® ACC 507–20, Germany). Prior to electrochemical measurements, the carbon material was purified at 450 °C for 3 h in nitrogen atmosphere to eliminate potential oxidation products (oxygen-based functionalities) from the carbon surface.

The nitrogen adsorption isotherm of the activated carbon electrode was recorded by ASAP 2460 analyser (Micromeritics®, USA) at 77 K. The specific surface area was calculated using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) equation and verified with the pore size distribution, calculated using the 2D non-local density functional theory (2D NLDFT) method [56,57]. The material was characterized by a type I isotherm and a strictly microporous structure; the BET and 2D NLDFT surface area was ca. 1800 m² g⁻¹.

An aqueous solution of K₂SO₄ salt at a concentration of 0.5 mol L⁻¹ was prepared by dissolving an appropriate mass of

K_2SO_4 salt ($\geq 99.0\%$, Sigma-Aldrich®) in distilled water. The pH value of ca. 6.1 and conductivity of ca. $79 \text{ mS}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ were measured by a pH- and conductivity-meter from Mettler Toledo®, Switzerland. Agar-based electrolytes were prepared by dissolving an appropriate mass of agar powder (Sigma-Aldrich® Poland, for microbiology, No. 05040-100G, batch BCBQ5150V) in $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} K_2SO_4$ solution and then heating the mixture in a microwave reactor until a homogenous gel was obtained. Microwave heating was used to avoid a heat gradient and inhomogeneous gel formation. The addition of agar did not influence the pH value. It has to be noted that the purity of the agar remarkably affects its electrochemical performance; ash content in the powder should be avoided.

2.2. Electrochemical cell assembly

The electrochemical measurements were performed in a symmetric, two-electrode Swagelok® cell and in a three-electrode set-up with a platinum mesh serving as the counter electrode; a Hg/Hg₂SO₄ reference electrode was used to monitor the electrode potentials. The electrodes were soaked in the various electrolytes prior to measurement and separated by a Whatman GFA/D porous membrane.

In the three-electrode measurement, the working electrode was impregnated in the agar-based electrolyte. The thickness of the gel electrolyte was $\sim 200 \mu\text{m}$. The contact between counter electrode and reference electrode was provided by $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} K_2SO_4$ aqueous solution.

2.3. Electrochemical techniques

The electrochemical measurements were conducted with a computer-controlled multichannel potentiostat/galvanostat (VMP3, Biologic®, France). The experimental techniques included galvanostatic charge/discharge within a $0.1\text{--}10 \text{ A g}^{-1}$ current load, cyclic voltammetry at 0.1 and $10 \text{ mV}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ scan rates and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy ($100 \text{ kHz}\text{--}100 \text{ mHz}$ for the *ac* frequency range and $\pm 5 \text{ mV}$ for the voltage amplitude). All current and capacitance values are expressed per mass of one electrode, if not stated otherwise.

2.4. Operando Raman electrochemical spectroscopy

Operando Raman spectroscopy was performed with a DXR-2 computer-controlled Raman microscope (ThermoFisher Scientific®, USA). The electrochemical investigation was performed in a customized three-electrode cell; the working electrode ($\varnothing = 5 \text{ mm}$) was placed behind a quartz glass window in perpendicular orientation to the laser beam (532 nm , adjusted power - 8 mW , spot size: $\sim 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ with a full range grating). Activated carbon impregnated with $2.5 \text{ wt}\%$ agar-based electrolyte served as the working electrode, platinum wire served as the counter electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode was used to control the potential.

Briefly, impregnated working electrode was placed in front of the glass window and the surroundings of the electrode were covered by the gel electrolyte. Such a construction prevented the access of aqueous electrolyte to the surface of the carbon. However, aqueous $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} K_2SO_4$ solution was applied to ensure good contact between the reference, counter and working electrode.

Raman spectra were continuously recorded every 5 min during cyclic voltammetry scanning at a $0.1 \text{ mV}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ scanning rate in a potential range from $+0.5$ to -1.75 V vs. NHE. Three consecutive cycles were recorded.

2.5. Internal pressure measurements

The gas generation rate was measured for a symmetric carbon/carbon system in a customized cell connected to the pressure sensor (Keller®, Switzerland). The electrode potentials were monitored by a Hg/Hg₂SO₄ reference electrode. To maintain controlled conditions, the cell was placed in a thermostatic chamber and stabilized for 6 h before the experiment. The internal pressure build-up was measured during 2 h of constant voltage holding for cell voltages of 1.0 V , 1.2 V , 1.4 V , 1.6 V and 1.8 V .

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 1 presents cyclic voltammograms recorded in the three-electrode cell at a $10 \text{ mV}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ scan rate for carbon electrodes operating in aqueous $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} K_2SO_4$ solution containing $0 \text{ wt}\%$, $1 \text{ wt}\%$, $2.5 \text{ wt}\%$ and $5 \text{ wt}\%$ of agar as an additive.

The vertex potential during the CV experiment was shifted gradually by 100 mV in the cathodic direction in the range $+0.5 \text{ V}$ vs. NHE to -1.75 V vs. NHE. The curves obtained for potential values above the hydrogen evolution potential (HEP = $-0.059\cdot\text{pH}$) resemble the typical shape associated with water reduction and hydrogen sorption [58]. Before reaching the HEP, a typical rectangular shape corresponding to electric double-layer (EDL) charging/discharging is observed. In fact, the change in current profile from capacitive to redox-based is observed far beyond the HEP. This suggests a high overpotential for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) in all electrolytes. It is worth noting that below the HEP, typical electrostatic charge accumulation in the electric double layer occurs. Above the HEP, water molecules are decomposed, and the produced nascent hydrogen is adsorbed either in the pores or on the surface of the active material; once the polarization is reversed, the oxidation of adsorbed hydrogen occurs. This is confirmed by the appearance of the oxidation peak during anodic polarization and is described by the following reaction:

A change in electrolyte (from liquid to gel-like) has an impact on the hydrogen sorption/desorption process. During cathodic polarization, a specific current value of -4072 mA g^{-1} was reached for

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammetry profiles (10 mV s^{-1}) of the Kynol® ACC 507-20 electrode, recorded in a three-electrode cell with $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} K_2SO_4$ electrolytes containing different amounts of agar.

the electrolyte containing 2.5 wt% agar; the electrodes operating with the electrolyte containing 1 wt% agar and without agar showed similar behaviour and reached -3848 mA g^{-1} and -3895 mA g^{-1} , respectively. The highest current value, i.e., -3613 mA g^{-1} , was recorded for the cell operating with 5 wt% agar. During anodic polarization, for samples without and with 1 wt% and 2.5 wt% agar, a gradual increase in desorption (oxidation) current can be observed: from 1844 mA g^{-1} for the cell without agar to 2090 mA g^{-1} and 2193 mA g^{-1} for the cells containing 1 wt% and 2.5 wt% agar, respectively. Furthermore, for these systems, the position of the oxidation peak is not influenced by the amount of agar added. In the case of the cell containing 5 wt% agar, the maximum desorption peak reaches a specific current value of 2063 mA g^{-1} and is shifted towards slightly higher potential values. This result indicates the influence of agar addition on the hydrogen storage process. In the case of electrolytes containing 1 wt% and 2.5 wt% agar, the change in electrolyte form contributed to a more efficient reaction, as indicated by the increase in the 'adsorption' and 'desorption' current. Most likely, this results from the fact that the increased viscosity of the electrolyte diminishes diffusion from the electrolyte surface towards the electrolyte bulk and 'keeps' the hydrogen ad-atoms at the interface. However, in the case of 5 wt% agar addition, the high viscosity of the electrolyte leads to the strengthening of hydrogen-hydrogen interactions in the electrolyte, and the activation energy for the hydrogen oxidation reaction is assumed to be higher; this behaviour is observed as a shift in the desorption peak towards higher potential values. This result might also be attributed to the change in the pH value in the vicinity of the electrode (towards lower values as the potential increases). Since cyclic voltammetry is considered a qualitative technique, these observations were verified via galvanostatic measurements.

Fig. 2 presents the results of the galvanostatic experiments, where the system was polarized towards cathodic potentials by applying a specific current of -1 A g^{-1} for 6 h (hydrogen storage) and then polarized towards a cut-off value (initial rest potential) with a specific current of $+50 \text{ mA g}^{-1}$.

All samples were oxidized until the same cut-off potential, and the desorption plateau, assigned to hydrogen oxidation, was observed at approximately -0.7 V vs. NHE. For ionogel electrolytes, a remarkable increase in reversible capacity is observed because the discharge plateau is much better defined.

Fig. 2. Galvanostatic profiles (50 mA g^{-1}) for Kynol® ACC 507–20 recorded in the three-electrode cell in $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ K}_2\text{SO}_4$ aqueous electrolyte with different amounts of agar; profiles recorded after 6 h at -1 A g^{-1} reduction.

This result confirms previous observations where in the case of 1 and 2.5 wt% agar content, a higher sorption and desorption current was observed. In the case of 5 wt% agar, the shift in desorption peak suggests stronger interactions between hydrogen ad-atoms and the carbon surface. Once the hydrogen desorption process is finished, the capacitive discharge of the electric double layer follows. For the samples without agar and with 1 and 2.5 wt% agar, the slope is nearly the same, which indicates a similar double-layer capacitance. Interestingly, in the electrolyte containing 5 wt% agar, the double-layer capacitance value seems to be the highest; however, the oxidation plateau is not well defined; hence, the pseudocapacitive contribution cannot be neglected. The 1st derivatives of the galvanostatic profiles (dashed lines in Fig. 2) show that the peak maxima move towards higher charge values. This attribute might be especially interesting in hybrid energy storage systems, where adjustment of the electrode potentials by mass and balance is crucial for the system life span.

Although hydrogen storage in porous carbons has already been confirmed in aqueous media by various techniques [58–67], the specific electrolytes applied in our study required additional confirmation.

Raman spectra recorded in *operando* mode for the hydrogen sorption/desorption process on the carbon electrode in a $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ K}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution with 2.5 wt% agar electrolyte are presented in Fig. 3.

As is typical of disordered carbons, two characteristic peaks, namely, the D-band at $\sim 1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the G-band at $\sim 1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, are observed. The existence of a so-called D-band is still not well understood; its appearance in the Raman spectrum is often explained either by a decrease in symmetry near microcrystalline edges or by the existence of specific vibrations at the matrix edges, induced, e.g., by oxides or C=C groups, normally present only at the edges. In contrast, the existence of the so-called G-band is fully understood and corresponds to an ideal graphitic lattice vibration mode [68,69].

Fig. 3 shows the so-called heat map graph resulting from Raman scattering during three cycles of cyclic voltammetry at a $0.1 \text{ mV} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ scanning rate in the range from -1.250 to $+0.450 \text{ V}$ vs. NHE. The changes in Raman intensity recorded during the experiment are distinguished by changes in colour from blue to red, which correspond to the lowest and highest intensity values, respectively. During cathodic polarization, down to an electrode potential

Fig. 3. Raman spectra heat map of Kynol® ACC 507–20 recorded in the three-electrode cell with $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ K}_2\text{SO}_4$ and 2.5% agar during 0.1 mV s^{-1} cyclic voltammetry scan. Spectra were recorded every 5 min. The top graph shows the electrochemical behaviour of the carbon electrode during the experiment. The left graph shows the section of Raman spectra used for transformation into a heat map.

of -0.5 V vs. NHE, charge is accumulated in the electric double layer. This process is reflected by the D and G band intensity increase due to ion adsorption on the electrode surface and the change in electrode volume resulting from the increasing interlayer distance between graphene sheets. Polarization towards lower potential values results in a further increase in the 1500 cm^{-1} band intensity, which is related to the initial step of the hydrogen storage process. The most remarkable changes are observed for the G-band, D-band and 1100 cm^{-1} band, related to the C_{sp^2} -H bending vibration and the C=C stretching vibration in amorphous carbons [70].

After changing the polarization, a further increase in D- and G-band intensities can be observed for potentials ranging from -0.75 V to $+0.2$ V vs. NHE. The maximum Raman intensity is correlated with the maximum desorption peak on the CV profile. This might be explained by the formation of edges in the 'crystalline' domains caused by the hydrogenation of carbon atoms. As claimed by other authors, such a shift in D- and G-band intensity might be attributed to slower carbon hydrogenation for strongly oxidized carbons, where carbon-hydrogen bonds are formed through the reduction of carbon-oxygen surface complexes under cathodic conditions [66]. During further polarization towards $+0.4$ V vs. NHE, a decrease in the D- and G-band intensity is observed. Such observations confirm the reversibility of the hydrogen sorption process. However, the intensity of these bands remains higher than during initial cathodic polarization, which indicates permanent changes in the carbon structure caused by hydrogen sorption.

To obtain more in-depth information about the hydrogen storage process, deconvolution of the spectra obtained during the reduction and oxidation process was performed. Experimental data and the fitted curves are shown in Fig. 4 A-C.

The calculated D/G band intensity ratio of 3.03 suggests that the material is highly amorphous. However, during the reduction process, some kind of ordering of the carbon structure can be observed as the D/G band intensity ratio decreases to 2.90. Moreover, the increase in the C_{sp^2} -H band intensity clearly indicates that hydrogen storage is in progress. Surprisingly, during oxidation, the C=C band intensity is lowered, but this might be related to the initial reduction of oxygen-based carbon functionalities and final removal of oxygen, which is then replaced by hydrogen. This is confirmed by the increase in C=C band intensity during oxidation, where hydrogen probably replaced oxygen groups. The hydrogen desorption process is confirmed by a decrease in the C_{sp^2} -H band intensity and an increase in the D/G band intensity ratio.

Thus, the agar-based solutions appear to be promising electrolytes for electrochemical capacitors.

Fig. 5 shows the capacitance vs. voltage performance, Ragone plots and long-term performance of systems with and without agar.

The capacitance values of the systems with electrolyte modified with agar were lower than those for systems operating with liquid electrolyte. The most remarkable capacitance loss was observed for the system with electrolyte modified with 1 wt% agar. For the cells with electrolytes containing 2.5 wt% and 5 wt% agar, a similar capacitance loss was observed.

The loss of capacitance for the cell with 1 wt% agar might originate from the poor mechanical properties (inelasticity) of the gel. For the cell with 5 wt% agar, the low efficiency might originate from the high density of the material and its very limited conductivity. The best result for a hydrogel material was obtained for the sample with a 2.5 wt% agar concentration, which was characterized by moderate conductivity and good mechanical properties (elasticity). According to the Raman spectra observations, one might assume that gel electrolyte improves the hydrogen sorption/desorption reaction reversibility, reflected as higher energy

Fig. 4. Deconvolution of Raman spectra: (A) initial, (B) during reduction, and (C) during oxidation of the carbon material Kynol® ACC 507–20 in 0.5 mol L^{-1} K_2SO_4 and 2.5% agar.

efficiency. For the cell operating with 2.5 wt% agar content, the energy efficiency is the highest, $88 \pm 3\%$ for a capacitor voltage of 1.6 V. In the case of the cell with 5 wt% agar, the efficiency does not change substantially with voltage.

Energy and power performance were evaluated by galvanostatic charge/discharge experiments for current densities ranging from $0.1\text{ A}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ to $10\text{ A}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, and the results are presented in the form of a Ragone plot in Fig. 5B. Despite lower capacitance values for the systems operating with electrolytes modified with agar, such systems are characterized by similar energy performance.

Fig. 5. (A) Capacitance vs. voltage performance (1 A g⁻¹), where the inset shows the charge discharge energy efficiency, (B) Ragone plot, and (C) cycle performance of capacitors with Kynol® ACC 507–20 in 0.5 mol L⁻¹ K₂SO₄ with different amounts of agar.

The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy results indicate that in the case of agar-modified electrolytes, the power performance is limited by a slightly higher internal resistance (by means of the equivalent series resistance, ESR), i.e., 0.41 Ohm for the sample without agar and 0.93 Ohm for the sample with 2.5 wt% agar, and lower ion mobility (by means of the equivalent distributed resistance, EDR), i.e., 1.62 Ohm for the sample without agar and 1.9 Ohm for the sample with 2.5 wt% agar. This effect is typical of solid-state electrolytes. However, in this case, the increase in resistance is negligible.

In the next step, the long-term performance was evaluated. The cells were charged/discharged with a 1 A g⁻¹ current density. The systems were tested at two voltage limits, i.e., 1.5 V, which is considered the maximum voltage for aqueous systems, and at elevated voltage, i.e., 1.6 V. The results are presented as the change in capacitance with respect to the initial state (Fig. 5C). According to the international standard, a capacitance drop of 20% from the initial value is considered the end of life of a capacitor. Interestingly, the performance of both systems is similar; thus, one can conclude that modification of the electrolyte has no remarkable impact on the long-term performance.

In addition to cyclability performance, capacitors with agar-based electrolytes were subjected to self-discharge measurements. Briefly, the systems were charged with a constant current load to a certain voltage and then left under open-circuit conditions for 12 h. After that time, the voltage was measured.

As expected, the change in electrolyte form significantly impacts the self-discharge of the capacitors compared to that in the system with liquid electrolyte. It is clearly visible that the systems with agar-based electrolytes are capable of maintaining the voltage for a longer time than the system with liquid electrolyte. The charge redistribution impact (observed just after polarization stops) is considerably diminished, most likely due to the immobilization of ions at the carbon/electrolyte interface. As the maximum voltage increases, the difference in self-discharge performance becomes less pronounced, but this difference in performance is caused by another self-discharge mechanism.

To identify the driving force of the self-discharge process, the voltage profiles were plotted against log(t), as shown in Fig. 6 B–C. For the cells charged to 1.6 V or less with the electrolytes modified with agar, two stages of diffusion-controlled processes can be distinguished: a first rapid drop in voltage, related to the charge redistribution after current cut-off, and a second drop, which is diffusion-controlled self-discharge due to reorganization of ions inside the pores. The results again confirm that a change in electrolyte form diminishes the charge redistribution effect.

Increasing the capacitor voltage to higher values, i.e., 1.8 V, promotes the involvement of a kinetic-driven process. This process can be observed as a three-stage self-discharge process. As in the previous cases, the initial linear loss of voltage is a diffusion-controlled process. Then, the linear profile of the voltage drop changes. This change becomes more visible as the initial voltage increases. A different profile of the voltage drop indicates that the self-discharge driving force has changed and kinetic self-discharge is now predominant. Finally, the profile transforms again into linear form, indicating diffusion-controlled self-discharge [71].

The self-discharge curves for the cells with liquid electrolyte are shown in Fig. 6C. It can be observed that diffusion-controlled voltage loss is observed only up to 1.2 V. Increasing the voltage to 1.4–1.8 V reveals a three-stage self-discharge process and involves an activation-controlled process, which is more pronounced for higher cut-off voltages. The difference in the profiles is related to more effective hydrogen storage in agar-based electrolytes. It is well accepted that for liquid electrolytes, the limit of activation-controlled self-discharge is approximately 1.2 V, which is roughly equal to the water decomposition voltage.

Finally, the results confirm that immobilization of ions at the electrode/electrolyte interface has a crucial impact on self-discharge limitation. Furthermore, more effective hydrogen storage within the carbon electrode matrix eliminates self-driven hydrogen desorption as a voltage loss component. Since water decomposition products at elevated voltages might lead to serious device damage, gel-like electrolytes are expected to diminish this phenomenon. Therefore, the internal pressure build-up and gas evolution in the system were monitored. The results of this

Fig. 6. (A) Loss of voltage over 12 h under open-circuit conditions and self-discharge profiles vs. $\log(t)$ of symmetric capacitors with Kynol® ACC 507–20 in $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ K}_2\text{SO}_4$ with 2.5% (B) and without agar (C).

Fig. 7. Terminal potentials of the electrodes and associated pressure build-up for systems without (A) and with 2.5 wt% agar (B).

measurement are presented in Fig. 7, where the terminal potentials of the electrodes vs. cell voltage and corresponding gas generation rate are shown.

It can be observed that the addition of agar changes the potential ranges of both the positive and negative electrodes. In particular, this behaviour can be observed in terms of anodic polarization, where the electrode potential does not exceed the oxygen evolution potential even at a 1.8 V capacitor voltage, while for the liquid electrolyte, the mentioned potential is reached when the system is charged to 1.4 V. In the case of the negative electrode, in both cases, the working potentials are far below the theoretical hydrogen evolution potentials. The pressure changes in the systems were recorded during 2 h of constant voltage holding in charged state at 30°C . The gas generation rate was calculated from the slope of the pressure change. Typical behaviour is observed, where the gas generation rate increases with voltage. For the system with liquid electrolyte, the starting point of pressure build-up in the

system is 1.4 V and corresponds to the oxygen evolution potential on the positive electrode. A further increase in the capacitor voltage causes an exponential increase in the gas generation rate. As shown by He et al. [72], the increase in pressure is connected with carbon oxidation and the evolution of CO and CO₂ gases on the positive electrode at 1.2 V and H₂ generation on the negative electrode after exceeding 1.8 V. This process is significantly limited when a gel-like electrolyte is applied. A constant increase in internal pressure is not observed until the system reaches 1.6 V. Nevertheless, the gas generation rate at this point is 4 times lower than that in the case of the liquid electrolyte, and at 1.8 V, the rate is 2.5 times lower. This indicates the suppression of carbon oxidation, resulting in CO and CO₂ evolution. Moreover, a more efficient hydrogen storage process might limit H₂ generation and evolution as a pressure increase component.

Keeping in mind all abovementioned facts, the following mechanism of the agar-based electrolyte might be assumed: higher affinity of the agar-based electrolyte to the activated carbon surface improves the penetration of the electrolyte and develops the electrode/electrolyte interface. This feature results in slightly higher capacitance values and improved charge propagation. Taking into account the viscoelastic properties of the gel-like electrolyte, one might assume that the ions (present in the polymer matrix) are immobilized in the vicinity of the electrode surface and their mobility is diminished. This impacts the charge redistribution, leakage current densities and self-discharge. As already mentioned, for capacitors operating with the agar-based electrolyte, leakage currents and self-discharge are diminished in comparison to the conventional electrolyte. This assumption is valid for the typical capacitive storage region, i.e. below water decomposition voltage.

At higher capacitor voltages, i.e. above water decomposition voltage, agar-based electrolyte improves the hydrogen storage and oxidation efficiency on the negative electrode. Improved hydrogen storage allows the electrode potential to be maintained at the appropriate level and prevents the self-discharge process that might be provoked by weakly bonded hydrogen. On one hand, the strength of the carbon-hydrogen bond has not been directly investigated in our study. On the other hand, self-discharge experiment realized in three-electrode cell with individual electrode potential monitoring indicates that the negative electrode maintains its potential at more cathodic values in agar-based electrolytes. Furthermore, internal pressure measurements indicated that the gas evolution for the capacitor with gel-like electrolyte is diminished.

We do not assume that chemical structure of the agar-based electrolyte is changed during electrochemical polarization, as the Raman spectra do not demonstrate any significant change even at extreme potential values. Certainly, during long-term operation, typical chemical degradation cannot be excluded. This aspect will be studied in the future.

Considering the molecular level, we assume that the chemical nature of agar improves the wettability of the electrode, mainly due to -SO₄ group presence. Proton-conducting mechanism cannot be confirmed yet.

Given that, in our opinion reduced self-discharge originates from viscoelastic properties of the gel-like electrolyte while the improved charge-propagation results from chemical composition of agar-based matrix.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we demonstrate the effect of applying a gel-like electrolyte on the hydrogen sorption phenomenon and the overall impact on the performance of electrochemical capacitors. In

terms of hydrogen storage, the application of gel-like electrolytes results in an increase in the volume of captured hydrogen and the strengthening of the formed bonds. The process of hydrogen storage in agar-based electrolytes was confirmed by Raman spectroscopy. Changes in the C_{sp2}-H band intensity during reduction indicate chemical hydrogen sorption, while changes in the C=C band correspond to reduction of the highly oxidized carbon surface. The fluctuating change in D/G band intensity confirms the reversibility of the hydrogen storage process. However, a higher efficiency of hydrogen storage in the three-electrode cell did not strictly reflect electrochemical capacitor performance. Agar-based systems were characterized by similar power and energy performance to those of liquid counterparts. The addition of agar also did not influence the cycle performance of capacitors. However, solidification of the electrolyte has a strong impact on the self-discharge and internal pressure build-up properties. The addition of agar to the electrolyte limited both diffusion- and kinetic-driven self-discharge processes by lowering ion mobility and improving the hydrogen sorption efficiency. Furthermore, agar-based electrolytes limit the carbon oxidation process, leading to increases in CO and CO₂ generation rates by 4 times at 1.6 V and 2.5 times at 1.8 V.

In comparison to previous reports, the presented system is characterized by an improved power/energy profile. The application of SO₄²⁻ as a charge carrier allowed the maximum capacitor voltage to be increased up to 1.5 V, in comparison to 1.0 V for the previously presented aqueous gel system.

Moreover, by avoiding NaCl as a conducting salt within the polymer matrix, the accelerated system corrosion caused by chloride ions is eliminated. Capacitors operating with gel-like membranes based on agar as the electrolytic medium were characterized by good cycling stability, similar to that of liquid counterparts. Importantly, the self-discharge and gas generation rates were significantly limited.

Additionally, a one-pot preparation method and in-situ gelation of the electrolyte on the electrode surface are expected to limit the costs of the full device; this might be another advantage over systems with ionic liquids.

Overall, the presented bio-compatible electrolyte for electrochemical capacitors is a step towards the preparation of systems with high energy efficiency and low self-discharge, which is a significant improvement in terms of saving operational costs. Moreover, reduced internal pressure build-up remarkably improves the stability of the systems from a long-term perspective.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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References

- [1] J. Baxter, Z.X. Bian, G. Chen, D. Danielson, M.S. Dresselhaus, A.G. Fedorov, T.S. Fisher, C.W. Jones, E. Maginn, U. Kortshagen, A. Manthiram, A. Nozik,

- D.R. Rolison, T. Sands, L. Shi, D. Sholl, Y.Y. Wu, Nanoscale design to enable the revolution in renewable energy, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 2 (2009) 559–588.
- [2] C. Liu, F. Li, L.P. Ma, H.M. Cheng, Advanced materials for energy storage, *Adv. Mater.* 22 (2010) E28–E62.
- [3] D.S. Su, G. Centi, A perspective on carbon materials for future energy application, *J. Energy Chem.* 22 (2013) 151–173.
- [4] Z.J. Jia, B.G. Wang, S.Q. Song, Y.S. Fan, Blue energy: current technologies for sustainable power generation from water salinity gradient, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 31 (2014) 91–100.
- [5] C. Cader, P. Bertheau, P. Blechinger, H. Huyskens, C. Breyer, Global cost advantages of autonomous solar-battery-diesel systems compared to diesel-only systems, *Energy Sustain. Dev.* 31 (2016) 14–23.
- [6] J. Khan, M.H. Arsalan, Solar power technologies for sustainable electricity generation – a review, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 55 (2016) 414–425.
- [7] A.G. Olabi, Renewable energy and energy storage systems, *Energy* 136 (2017) 1–6.
- [8] F. Bensebaa, Clean energy, *Interface Sci Techno* 19 (2013) 279–383.
- [9] P. Nunes, T. Farias, M.C. Brito, Enabling solar electricity with electric vehicles smart charging, *Energy* 87 (2015) 10–20.
- [10] R. Kötz, M. Carlen, Principles and applications of electrochemical capacitors, *Electrochim. Acta* 45 (2000) 2483–2498.
- [11] P. Simon, Y. Gogotsi, Materials for electrochemical capacitors, *Nat. Mater.* 7 (2008) 845–854.
- [12] J.R. Miller, A.F. Burke, Electrochemical capacitors: challenges and opportunities for real-world applications, *Electrochemical Society Interface* 17 (2008) 53–57.
- [13] J.J. Niu, B.E. Conway, W.G. Pell, Comparative studies of self-discharge by potential decay and float-current measurements at C double-layer capacitor and battery electrodes, *J. Power Sources* 135 (2004) 332–343.
- [14] A.M. Oickle, H.A. Andreas, Examination of water electrolysis and oxygen reduction as self-discharge mechanisms for carbon-based, aqueous electrolyte electrochemical capacitors, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 115 (2011) 4283–4288.
- [15] J.W. Graydon, M. Panjehshahi, D.W. Kirk, Charge redistribution and ionic mobility in the micropores of supercapacitors, *J. Power Sources* 245 (2014) 822–829.
- [16] M. Ishikawa, M. Ihara, M. Morita, Y. Matsuda, Electric double-layer capacitors with new gel electrolytes, *Electrochim. Acta* 40 (1995) 2217–2222.
- [17] M. Morita, M. Ishikawa, Y. Matsuda, Ionic conductivities of polymeric solid electrolyte films containing rare earth ions, *J. Alloy. Comp.* 250 (1997) 524–527.
- [18] M. Ishikawa, L. Yamamoto, M. Morita, Y. Ando, Performance of electric double layer capacitors with gel electrolytes containing an asymmetric ammonium salt, *Electrochemistry* 69 (2001) 437–439.
- [19] M. Morita, A. Tanaka, N. Yoshimoto, M. Ishikawa, Polymeric gel electrolytes using a network matrix with carbonyl groups for rechargeable lithium batteries, *Solid State Ion.* 152 (2002) 161–167.
- [20] K. Nakayama, Y. Honda, T. Sugimoto, H. Arima, H. Nakagawa, M. Ishikawa, Development of Gel Electrolyte Suitable for Electric Double Layer Capacitor, 2005, pp. 4569–4570.
- [21] M. Armand, F. Endres, D.R. MacFarlane, H. Ohno, B. Scrosati, Ionic-liquid materials for the electrochemical challenges of the future, *Nat. Mater.* 8 (2009) 621–629.
- [22] K. Lian, C.M. Li, Solid polymer electrochemical capacitors using heteropoly acid electrolytes, *Electrochem. Commun.* 11 (2009) 22–24.
- [23] S. Yamazaki, A. Takegawa, Y. Kaneko, J. Kadokawa, M. Yamagata, M. Ishikawa, An acidic cellulose-chitin hybrid gel as novel electrolyte for an electric double layer capacitor, *Electrochem. Commun.* 11 (2009) 68–70.
- [24] J. Le Bideau, L. Viau, A. Vioux, Ionogels, Ionic liquid based hybrid materials, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 40 (2011) 907–925.
- [25] S.T. Senthilkumar, R.K. Selvan, N. Ponpandian, J.S. Melo, Redox additive aqueous polymer gel electrolyte for an electric double layer capacitor, *RSC Adv.* 2 (2012) 8937–8940.
- [26] M. Yamagata, K. Soeda, S. Ikebe, S. Yamazaki, M. Ishikawa, Chitosan-based gel electrolyte containing an ionic liquid for high-performance nonaqueous supercapacitors, *Electrochim. Acta* 100 (2013) 275–280.
- [27] F. Lufitano, P. Staiti, M. Minutoli, Influence of nafion content in electrodes on performance of carbon supercapacitors, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 151 (2004) A64–A68.
- [28] F. Lufitano, P. Staiti, Performance improvement of Nafion based solid state electrochemical supercapacitor, *Electrochim. Acta* 49 (2004) 2683–2689.
- [29] J. Qiao, N. Yoshimoto, M. Ishikawa, M. Morita, A proton conductor based on a polymeric complex of poly(ethylene oxide)-modified poly(methacrylate) with anhydrous H₃PO₄, *Chem. Mater.* 15 (2003) 2005–2010.
- [30] K.W. Park, H.J. Ahn, Y.E. Sung, All-solid-state supercapacitor using a Nafion® polymer membrane and its hybridization with a direct methanol fuel cell, *J. Power Sources* 109 (2002) 500–506.
- [31] P. Staiti, M. Minutoli, F. Lufitano, All solid electric double layer capacitors based on Nafion ionomer, *Electrochim. Acta* 47 (2002) 2795–2800.
- [32] M. Morita, S. Kitamura, M. Ishikawa, Y. Matsuda, Electrocatalytic activity of cerium(III) incorporated in a Nafion film on a glassy carbon support, *Denki Kagaku* 65 (1997) 490–492.
- [33] M. Armand, Polymers with ionic-conductivity, *Adv. Mater.* 2 (1990) 278–286.
- [34] Z. Gadjourova, Y.G. Andreev, D.P. Tunstall, P.G. Bruce, Ionic conductivity in crystalline polymer electrolytes, *Nature* 412 (2001) 520–523.
- [35] T.H. Epps, T.S. Bailey, H.D. Pham, F.S. Bates, Phase behavior of lithium perchlorate-doped poly(styrene-*b*-isoprene-*b*-ethylene oxide) triblock copolymers, *Chem. Mater.* 14 (2002) 1706–1714.
- [36] A. Lewandowski, M. Zajder, E. Frackowiak, F. Beguin, Supercapacitor based on activated carbon and polyethylene oxide-KOH-H₂O polymer electrolyte, *Electrochim. Acta* 46 (2001) 2777–2780.
- [37] H.Y. Yu, J.H. Wu, L.Q. Fan, K.Q. Xu, X. Zhong, Y.Z. Lin, J.M. Lin, Improvement of the performance for quasi-solid-state supercapacitor by using PVA-KOH-KI polymer gel electrolyte, *Electrochim. Acta* 56 (2011) 6881–6886.
- [38] Z.S. Wu, K. Parvez, X.L. Feng, K. Mullen, Graphene-based in-plane micro-supercapacitors with high power and energy densities, *Nat. Commun.* 4 (2013).
- [39] X.J. Liu, T. Osaka, All-solid-state electric double-layer capacitor with isotropic high-density graphite electrode and polyethylene oxide/LiClO₄ polymer electrolyte, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 143 (1996) 3982–3986.
- [40] M. Morita, J.L. Qiao, N. Yoshimoto, M. Ishikawa, Application of proton conducting electrolytes to electrochemical capacitors, *Electrochim. Acta* 50 (2004) 837–841.
- [41] E. Armelin, M.M. Perez-Madriral, C. Aleman, D.D. Diaz, Current status and challenges of biohydrogels for applications as supercapacitors and secondary batteries, *J. Mater. Chem.* 4 (2016) 8952–8968.
- [42] M. Yamagata, K. Soeda, S. Yamazaki, M. Ishikawa, Charge-discharge behavior of electric double layer capacitor with alginate/ionic liquid gel electrolyte, battery/energy technology (general) – 216th, Ecs Meeting 25 (2010) 193–200.
- [43] M. Yamagata, S. Ikebe, Y. Kasai, K. Soeda, M. Ishikawa, Dramatic improvements in electric double-layer capacitors using polysaccharides, *Electrochemical Capacitors* 50 (2013) 27–36.
- [44] H.B. Huang, X.P. Zeng, W. Li, H. Wang, Q. Wang, Y.J. Yang, Reinforced conducting hydrogels prepared from the in situ polymerization of aniline in an aqueous solution of sodium alginate, *J. Mater. Chem.* 2 (2014) 16516–16522.
- [45] M.M. Perez-Madriral, F. Estrany, E. Armelin, D.D. Diaz, C. Aleman, Towards sustainable solid-state supercapacitors: electroactive conducting polymers combined with biohydrogels, *J. Mater. Chem.* 4 (2016) 1792–1805.
- [46] J. Zeng, L. Wei, X. Guo, Bio-inspired high-performance solid-state supercapacitors with the electrolyte, separator, binder and electrodes entirely from kelp, *J. Mater. Chem.* 5 (2017) 25282–25292.
- [47] N.A. Choudhury, P.W.C. Northrop, A.C. Crothers, S. Jain, V.R. Subramanian, Chitosan hydrogel-based electrode binder and electrolyte membrane for EDLCs: experimental studies and model validation, *J. Appl. Electrochem.* 42 (2012) 935–943.
- [48] W.G. Moon, G.P. Kim, M. Lee, H.D. Song, J. Yi, A biodegradable gel electrolyte for use in high-performance flexible supercapacitors, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 7 (2015) 3503–3511.
- [49] R.K. Pal, S.C. Kundu, V.K. Yadavalli, Fabrication of flexible, fully organic, degradable energy storage devices using silk proteins, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (2018) 9620–9628.
- [50] V. Normand, D.L. Lootens, E. Amici, K.P. Plucknett, P. Aymard, New insight into agarose gel mechanical properties, *Biomacromolecules* 1 (2000) 730–738.
- [51] H.J. Koo, S.T. Chang, J.M. Slocik, R.R. Naik, O.D. Velev, Aqueous soft matter based photovoltaic devices, *J. Mater. Chem.* 21 (2011) 72–79.
- [52] K. Fic, G. Lota, M. Meller, E. Frackowiak, Novel insight into neutral medium as electrolyte for high-voltage supercapacitors, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5 (2012) 5842–5850.
- [53] Q. Gao, L. Demarconnay, E. Raymundo-Pinero, F. Beguin, Exploring the large voltage range of carbon/carbon supercapacitors in aqueous lithium sulfate electrolyte, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5 (2012) 9611–9617.
- [54] L. Demarconnay, E. Raymundo-Pinero, F. Beguin, A symmetric carbon/carbon supercapacitor operating at 1.6 V by using a neutral aqueous solution, *Electrochem. Commun.* 12 (2010) 1275–1278.
- [55] P. Ratajczak, K. Jurewicz, P. Skowron, Q. Abbas, F. Beguin, Effect of accelerated ageing on the performance of high voltage carbon/carbon electrochemical capacitors in salt aqueous electrolyte, *Electrochim. Acta* 130 (2014) 344–350.
- [56] J. Jagiello, J.P. Olivier, A simple two-dimensional NLDFT model of gas adsorption in finite carbon pores. Application to pore structure analysis, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 113 (2009) 19382–19385.
- [57] J. Jagiello, J.P. Olivier, 2D-NLDFT adsorption models for carbon slit-shaped pores with surface energetical heterogeneity and geometrical corrugation, *Carbon* 55 (2013) 70–80.
- [58] F. Béguin, M. Friebe, K. Jurewicz, C. Vix-Guterl, J. Dentzer, E. Frackowiak, State of hydrogen electrochemically stored using nanoporous carbons as negative electrode materials in an aqueous medium, *Carbon* 44 (2006) 2392–2398.
- [59] K. Jurewicz, E. Frackowiak, F. Beguin, Electrochemical storage of hydrogen in activated carbons, *Fuel Process. Technol.* 77 (2002) 415–421.
- [60] K. Jurewicz, E. Frackowiak, F. Beguin, Towards the mechanism of electrochemical hydrogen storage in nanostructured carbon materials, *Appl Phys A-Mater* 78 (2004) 981–987.
- [61] F. Beguin, K. Jurewicz, M. Friebe, E. Frackowiak, Advantages of electrochemical hydrogen storage over gas adsorption in nanoporous carbons, *Ann Chim-Sci Mat* 30 (2005) 531–539.
- [62] K. Jurewicz, E. Frackowiak, F. Beguin, Nanoporous H-sorbed carbon as anode of secondary cell, *J. Power Sources* 188 (2009) 617–620.
- [63] K. Babel, D. Janasiak, K. Jurewicz, Electrochemical hydrogen storage in activated carbons with different pore structures derived from certain lignocellulose materials, *Carbon* 50 (2012) 5017–5026.
- [64] J.P. Mathieu, M. Lounsbury, The Raman spectra of metallic nitrates and the structure of concentrated solutions of electrolytes, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*

- (1950) 196–&.
- [65] S. Osswald, Y. Gogotsi, In Situ Raman Spectroscopy of Oxidation of Carbon Nanomaterials, *Raman Spectroscopy for Nanomaterials Characterization* (2012) 291–351.
- [66] S. Leyva-García, E. Morallon, D. Cazorla-Amoros, F. Beguin, D. Lozano-Castello, New insights on electrochemical hydrogen storage in nanoporous carbons by in situ Raman spectroscopy, *Carbon* 69 (2014) 401–408.
- [67] K. Fic, M. He, E.J. Berg, P. Novák, E. Frackowiak, Comparative operando study of degradation mechanisms in carbon-based electrochemical capacitors with Li₂SO₄ and LiNO₃ electrolytes, *Carbon* 120 (2017) 281–293.
- [68] M.J. Bleda-Martinez, J.M. Perez, A. Linares-Solana, E. Morallon, D. Cazorla-Amoros, Effect of surface chemistry on electrochemical storage of hydrogen in porous carbon materials, *Carbon* 46 (2008) 1053–1059.
- [69] F. Tuinstra, J.L. Koenig, Raman spectrum of graphite, *J. Chem. Phys.* 53 (1970) 1126–1130.
- [70] K. Fic, M. Meller, E. Frackowiak, Interfacial redox phenomena for enhanced aqueous supercapacitors, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 162 (2015) A5140–A5147.
- [71] L. Garcia-Cruz, P. Ratajczak, J. Iniesta, V. Montiel, F. Beguin, Self-discharge of AC/AC electrochemical capacitors in salt aqueous electrolyte, *Electrochim. Acta* 202 (2016) 66–72.
- [72] M. He, K. Fic, E. Frackowiak, P. Novák, E.J. Berg, Ageing Phenomena in High-Voltage Aqueous Supercapacitors Investigated by in Situ Gas Analysis, *Energy and Environmental Science*, 2016.